

Computer Augmented Modelling of Complexes of Amino Acids in Aquo-organic Mixtures. Part-I. Acido-basic Equilibria of L-Alanine and L-Dopa in Aquo-DMSO Media[†]

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The mathematical modelling of acido-basic equilibria of L-alanine and L-dopa in aquo-DMSO mixtures of 10–70% (v/v) is investigated. The approximate stability constants obtained using computer program *SCHEM(2.0)* were refined by the program *MINIQUAD 75*, which employs constrained least-squares together with the Marquardt algorithm. The increase in the formation constant of carboxyl proton was explained from electrostatic considerations. The minimum observed for the stability constants of amino proton was fitted into an empirical quadratic model. These empirical models are of immense importance to predict the equilibrium constants at desired cosolvent compositions of the same solvent mixture or similar isodielectric media and to calculate the effective dielectric constant or equivalent solution dielectric constant of biological active centres. Specific solute-solvent interactions were observed and a mechanism for the solvation of these ligands in DMSO is proposed. The main line and sub-routine *DINF* of *MINIQUAD75* are suitably modified for ease of data input.

ALTHOUGH a complete comprehension of chemical principles, biological reactions and medicinal aspects of human body are beyond reality, a systematic understanding of some of the reactions met in ordinary life (save anaemia, cancer or rickets) and making use of their differences from the normal processes opens new vistas in medical practice rather than a palative crutch. Because of the complexity of biological macromolecules and consequent difficulties in their study, the use of model compounds which have similar characteristics drew the attention of researchers in the last two decades. Amino acids and peptides have been proved to be good model compounds in protein research, in spite of inherent limitations due to the inadequacy of model compounds in understanding real life problems.

Investigations of acido-basic equilibria of amino acids, their interaction with metal ions in media of varied ionic strength, temperature and dielectric constant throw light on the mechanism of enzyme-catalysed reactions. Although it is known that the polarity of the active site cavities in proteins is lower than that of the bulk, a direct measurement of dielectric constant is not possible. Sigel¹ recently invoked a method wherein comparison of formation constants of acido-basic equilibria and/or metal complex equilibria with those at biological centre offer a way to estimate an effective dielectric constant or equivalent solution dielectric constant for the cavity. This brought a renaissance in the study of complex equilibria in aquo-organic mixtures apart

from its established utility in understanding solute-solvent interactions, increasing sensitivity of reactions of analytical and industrial importance and solubilising ligands or their metal complexes. In continuation of our studies in aquo-organic media², we have taken up a thorough investigation of complex equilibria of amino acids with first row transition metal ions employing rigorous mathematical procedures for obtaining best chemical model and studying solute-solvent interactions.

L-Dopa (3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine) is interesting not only for its functional groups but also for physiological and therapeutic effects which brought its studies in the foreground of biological, biochemical and pharmaceutical research. It is very effective therapeutic in Parkinson's disease³ and manganese poisoning. L-Dopa finds biochemical importance in neuro-transmission process⁴ and thus care is to be exercised in chronic L-dopa treatment because of the on-off side-effects⁵.

In spite of the fact that the complexes of L-dopa and L-alanine are subjected to a thorough investigation⁶ in aqueous solutions, their study in aquo-organic media is scarce. Collange and Paris⁷ investigated the ionisation equilibria of glycine and iodothyronines in aquo-DMSO medium by potentiometric and spectrophotometric techniques and observed that percentage of cosolvent at which minimum in log formation constants corresponding to phenolic and carboxyl protons were found to increase mono-

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tonously. Gergely and Kiss⁸ studied the interaction of L-alanine with proton and divalent metal ions in aquo-methanol and aquo-dioxane media by potentiometric and calorimetric techniques. They concluded that solute-solvent interactions play an important role in explaining the variation of thermodynamic quantities with cosolvent content.

The cosolvent chosen in this study is DMSO for various reasons. DMSO is a dipolar aprotic solvent with good ionising properties resulting in a stable dimethyl ion in solution⁹. Further, its dielectric constant and polarisability are appreciably greater than those of other solvents like methanol and acetonitrile, which results in different electrostatic and dispersion effects. The behaviour of protonation of anionic ligands markedly differs from hydroxyl solvents since DMSO is a better hydrogen bond acceptor. DMSO is easily purified¹⁰ to a high degree and it has a relatively basic oxygen atom solvating cations better than water.

We report herein the results of acido-basic equilibria of L-alanine and L-dopa in aquo-DMSO mixtures of 10–70% (v/v) by pH-metric method using MINQUAD 75¹¹ for the calculation of equilibrium constants.

Experimental

An aqueous solution (0.05 mol dm⁻³) of L-alanine (Sarabhai Chemicals) was prepared without further purification of the sample. Due to the limited solubility of L-dopa (Loba) an aquo-DMSO solution (0.05 mol dm⁻³) was prepared as and when required. The pessimistic error, calculated by FORTRAN 77 program COSWT (concentration of solution by weight method)¹² does not exceed 0.1006% for the ligands.

DMSO was purified¹³ by drying over calcium hydroxide and twice fractionally distilled at 0.5–3.0 mm/Hg pressure. All other solutions were of A.R. grade and aqueous solutions were prepared in double-distilled deionised water. The errors crept in the standardisation of sodium hydroxide were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification. The large *F* value (0.4358) indicated good precision of titrimetric results. An ELICO digital pH meter of 0.01 readability in conjunction with a glass and calomel electrode assembly was used to monitor the changes in the hydrogen ion concentration. The titration assembly and calibration of glass electrode in aquo-organic mixtures are described elsewhere.

Requisite volumes of sodium chloride solution to give an overall concentration of 0.15 mol dm⁻³ water, cosolvent (DMSO) and L-alanine or L-dopa solutions were added such that the overall percentage (v/v) of the cosolvent was in the range 10–70, while the concentration of the ligand was of the order of 0.01–0.02 mol dm⁻³ in the three different experiments. Hydrochloric acid (0.2 mol dm⁻³; 5.0 dm³) was then slowly added from a micro burette. After the addition of each aliquot (0.1 dm³) of sodium

hydroxide (0.4 mol dm⁻³) the pH meter reading was followed at regular intervals. The precision of the pH measurements estimated from duplicate titrations was ± 0.02 .

Results and Discussion

The approximate stability constants for L-alanine and L-dopa are calculated using SCPHD (2.0)¹⁴, a FORTRAN 77 program written in an user friendly mode. The output of this program helps in selecting the pH range for further investigation by a non-linear least-squares algorithm incorporated in MINQUAD 75. Our recent graphical method¹⁵ yields equilibrium constants comparable to those of linear least-squares even for phenolic protons unlike that of Irving and Rossotti procedure. The algorithm of input modules of SCPHD (2.0) is so designed that the same data file can be used with MINQUAD 75. In this connection the mainline and subroutine DINP of MINQUAD 75 are suitably modified.

L-Alanine or L-dopa has one carboxyl proton and an amino proton. L-Dopa, however, has an additional ionisable phenolic proton, and intensive investigations of Martin¹⁶ and Jameson¹⁷ resolved the controversy and concluded that phenolic proton is more acidic than protonated amine. Typical results of modelling study of acido-basic equilibria of these ligands with MINQUAD 75 are presented in Table 1. The best chemical model does not include the ionisation of second phenolic proton of L-dopa as the corresponding model was rejected based on the fact that the corresponding guess constant became negative during the refinement procedure. Further, L₂H_x type of species are not considered in aquo-DMSO media since no drift in formation curves is observed for different ligand concentrations (Fig. 1).

MINQUAD 75 does not have an inbuilt provision to study the effect of variation of parameters like error in p*K*_w, concentrations of ingredients, and calibration parameters of the electrode. In order to rely upon the best chemical model for critical evaluation, pessimistic errors of varied range are introduced into the experimental data and analysed with MINQUAD 75. A typical sample results (Table 2) emphasise stability constants corresponding to carboxyl protons are more affected than those of phenolic or amino protons.

Precision of proton-ligand stability constants—chemometric approach: The investigation of acido-basic equilibria primarily deals with pattern recognition of primary (pH vs volume) or secondary ($\bar{n}H$ = average number of protons bound per mole of ligand, and \bar{z} =average number of protons released per mole of ligand) data, a branch of chemometrics. It is concerned with the selection and validation of chemical model based on advanced statistical tests and optimisation procedures. In addition to recent developments in data acquisition systems (ion selectrometers, automatic titrators and robotics) the use of computers for fast number crunching and

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL MODEL OF ACIDO-BASIC EQUILIBRIA OF L-ALANINE AND L-DOPA*
Temp.=303 K, $\mu=0.15 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaCl) in aquo-DMSO mixtures

Cosolvent % (v/v)	$\log \beta_1$ (SD)	$\log \beta_2^*$ (SD)	$\log \beta_3$ (SD)	pH-range	NP	R	χ^2	Skewness	Kurtosis	$U/(NP-m) \times 10^3$
L-Alanine										
00.0	9.894 (0.003)	12.172 (0.005)		2.0-2.9 9.2-10.5	184	0.005	6.85	0.28	6.90	2.864
10.0	9.797 (0.007)	12.127 (0.011)		2.0-3.2 8.8-10.4	96	0.003	17.35	0.25	4.97	8.211
20.0	9.775 (0.004)	12.291 (0.006)		2.1-3.2 9.3-10.3	56	0.006	12.97	0.34	3.75	1.046
30.0	9.746 (0.006)	12.360 (0.010)		2.1-3.3 9.3-10.3	90	0.009	3.85	0.27	2.97	5.273
40.0	9.869 (0.005)	12.836 (0.009)		2.1-3.4 9.3-10.4	80	0.005	25.93	0.39	5.48	3.717
50.0	9.921 (0.005)	13.097 (0.010)		2.5-3.9 9.2-10.6	86	0.012	6.43	0.08	4.32	4.946
60.0	10.066 (0.001)	13.563 (0.012)		2.9-4.1 9.3-10.8	96	0.001	4.55	0.12	4.84	2.681
70.0	10.229 (0.007)	13.970 (0.018)		2.6-4.7 9.6-11.4	92	0.023	18.81	0.96	5.08	5.136
L-Dopa										
00.0	10.203 (0.008)	19.053 (0.009)	2.287 (0.012)	2.0-2.8 8.4-8.9 9.5-10.5	158	0.003	18.32	1.07	4.3	1.101
10.0	10.140 (0.004)	19.111 (0.005)	21.525 (0.009)	2.2-2.8 8.5-9.2 9.7-10.3	141	0.004	49.43	0.82	3.03	4.173
20.0	10.084 (0.004)	19.000 (0.006)	21.596 (0.012)	2.0-2.9 8.5-9.5 9.7-10.5	117	0.007	95.83	1.08	4.25	4.786
30.0	10.034 (0.008)	19.127 (0.009)	21.674 (0.020)	2.1-3.0 8.5-9.4 9.7-10.3	119	0.015	4.15	0.17	6.17	8.748
40.0	10.422 (0.006)	19.563 (0.009)	22.355 (0.014)	2.2-3.7 8.4-9.5 10.1-10.9	114	0.008	36.22	1.45	4.14	3.866
50.0	10.789 (0.006)	20.050 (0.010)	23.195 (0.016)	2.4-3.7 8.7-9.5 10.4-11.2	89	0.003	12.83	0.21	3.70	2.758
60.0	11.111 (0.006)	20.535 (0.007)	24.083 (0.009)	3.0-4.9 8.8-10.0 10.7-11.6	68	0.025	49.34	0.35	4.96	5.719

* $U = \sum_{i=1}^{NP} (TLC_i - TLE_i)^2 + (THC_i - THE_i)^2$; NP=number of points; SD=standard deviation in $\log \beta$; Shewness

$$= \sum_{i=1}^{NP} \sum_{x=L,H} (TXC_i - TXE_i)^2 / (NP \cdot \text{vav} \cdot \text{SD}).$$

expert system methodology for consistent decision making (using specialists knowledge and experience) brought renaissance in equilibrium chemistry.

The very low standard deviation in $\log \beta$ s and small values of U —sum of the squares of the deviation in concentrations of hydrogen ion and ligand for all experimental points—corrected for degrees of freedom reveal that (i) high precision of $\log \beta$ values and (ii) sufficient data points for each of the species detected and goodness of the fit of proposed model for the experimental data.

Residual analysis: ψ^2 statistic became popular in complex equilibria during the last one decade and the values reported either to range from ≈ 10 to 400 for systems of increasing complexity (proton-ligand to quaternary metal complexes). In the present investigation, they range between 3 and 26 for L-alanine and weighted residuals follow a part of normal distribution. However, the deviation of kurtosis (2 to 7) and skewness (0.08 to 1.4) from 3 and 0 respectively infer that the residuals concentrate more to the left of the peak. Crystallographic R-

Fig. 1. Formation curves of L-dopa in 30% DMSO-water mixture: (O) 0.01, (Δ) 0.015 and (\square) 0.02 mol dm⁻³.

factor test is used to conclude that even under present experimental conditions a three parameter model for L-dopa and two parameter model for L-alanine are needed. This test was primarily aimed at deciding whether inclusion of more species in the model results in significantly better agreement between the experimental and the calculated data.

The distribution diagrams produced by DISPLIT¹⁸ employing the stability constants in the best chemical model (Fig. 2) show that ionisation of carboxyl proton takes place around pH 2.5 while the ionisation of the phenolic and amino proton is simultaneous around pH 9.0. The plateau corresponds to

Fig. 2. Species distribution of L-alanine and L-dopa as a function of pH.

a stable zwitterion form of the ligand in the pH region 4.0–7.5 and the protonated form of amino group of L-dopa (LH⁻) reaches around 60% in 30% (v/v) DMSO. The acido-basic equilibria of the compounds can be represented as in Scheme 1.

Solute-solvent interactions: The three important factors in decreasing contribution to free energy representing the behaviour of an electrolyte in solution are ion-ion, ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions. Electrometric studies in aquo-organic media at constant ionic strength, however, do not take into consideration of ion-ion interactions.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SYSTEMATIC ERROR ON PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF L-ALANINE IN 20% (v/v) AQUO-DMSO MEDIA*

Ingradient % Error	Alkali		Mineral acid		Ligand	
	log β_1 (SD)	log β_2 (SD)	log β_1 (SD)	log β_2 (SD)	log β_1 (SD)	log β_2 (SD)
-5%	10.083 (0.021)	12.758 (0.023)	9.658 (0.008)	12.050 (0.012)	9.781 (0.009)	12.546 (0.014)
-2%	9.974 (0.011)	12.646 (0.017)	9.727 (0.005)	12.193 (0.008)	9.846 (0.007)	12.533 (0.012)
0%	9.775 (0.004)	12.291 (0.006)	9.775 (0.004)	12.291 (0.006)	9.775 (0.004)	12.291 (0.006)
+2%	9.799 (0.005)	12.408 (0.007)	9.817 (0.005)	12.383 (0.008)	9.781 (0.009)	12.546 (0.014)
+5%	9.824 (0.008)	12.432 (0.010)	9.885 (0.007)	12.526 (0.012)	9.973 (0.010)	12.510 (0.014)

*Only a few typical points are given.

Scheme 1

Assuming the validity of additive physicochemical model, free energy of ionisation of these amino acids in aquo-DMSO mixtures is split into three terms, viz. (i) the interaction of an ion of finite size in medium of uniform dielectric constant, (ii) specific interactions of all species with solvent at various distances resulting in multilayer solvation zones¹⁹, and (iii) complexes of definite composition between water and DMSO.

The literature data for the dielectric constant (*D*) of aquo-DMSO mixtures (w/w) were fitted into two curves by the method of orthogonal polynomials of third order due to Forsythe²⁰. From the residues (Tables 3 and 4), it is clear that prediction of *D* values for mixtures of desired v/v ratios can be employed for interpreting solute-solvent behaviour. A perusal of the variation of log formation constant for carboxyl and phenolic protons has a pronounced effect with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. Considering aquo-DMSO mixtures as a homogeneous, isotropic continuum, the ion-solvent interactions are determined by macroscopic physical properties like dielectric constant and refractive index of the solvent mixtures and size and charge of the solute. These long range interactions²¹ are referred as electrostatic, non-specific²² or universal solute-solvent interactions.

The analysis of variation of log *K* for the acidobasic equilibria of the ligands with various intrinsic parameters of solvent mixture is performed using the software ESOC (effect of solvent on complex equilibria)²³ developed in our laboratory. Since 1/*D* is a perfect linear function of (*D* - 1)/(2*D* + 1) (Fig. 3), the analysis of variation of log *K^M* with dielectric constant is confined to 1/*D*. The linear trends proposed by several investigators are due to the studies in limited range of solvent composition, and in fact,

TABLE 3—ORTHOGONAL POLYNOMIAL FIT OF DIELECTRIC CONSTANT WITH w/w % OF DMSO-WATER*

%	Observed	Calculated	Residue
$\alpha_0 = 79.264$	$\alpha_1 = -0.136$	$\alpha_2 = 0.003728$	$\alpha_3 = -0.00005245$
10.00	78.20	78.22	-0.0243
18.58	77.90	77.82	-0.0875
20.00	77.50	77.61	-0.0150
32.56	76.90	76.98	-0.0776
40.00	76.40	76.43	-0.0322
52.01	74.90	74.90	+0.0033
60.00	73.30	73.20	+0.1031
65.01	71.70	71.77	-0.0693

The variance of the fit = 0.0147

%	Observed	Calculated	Residue
$\alpha_0 = 131.0$	$\alpha_1 = -2.350$	$\alpha_2 = 0.0349$	$\alpha_3 = -0.0001984$
70.00	69.50	69.48	+0.0234
74.29	67.70	67.71	-0.0066
80.00	64.70	64.80	-0.1029
81.26	64.00	64.06	-0.0583
86.67	60.70	60.35	-0.3543
91.00	56.50	56.68	-0.1797
94.55	53.00	53.14	-0.1397
97.50	49.90	49.79	+0.1095

The variance of the fit = 0.05098

*Wt% = $\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 D + \alpha_2 D^2 + \alpha_3 D^3$ (*D* = dielectric constant).

TABLE 4—INTRINSIC PARAMETERS OF AQUO-DMSO MIXTURES*

%(v/v)	%(w/w)	<i>n_x</i>	<i>D</i>	log <i>F</i>
10	10.85	0.026 0	78.16	-0.030
20	21.50	0.056 0	77.54	-0.250
30	31.95	0.095 0	77.01	-0.375
40	42.21	0.140 0	76.22	-0.462
50	52.28	0.210 5	74.85	-0.544
60	62.17	0.280 0	72.62	-0.630
70	71.90	0.375 0	68.73	-0.840
80	81.42	0.505 0	63.96	—
90	90.79	0.695 0	56.88	—

**n_x* = mole fraction of the DMS, *D* = dielectric constant calculated from orthogonal fit.

non-linear relationship and unusual behaviour is not uncommon. As the shapes of the curves do not suggest a higher order polynomial trend, we have arrived at a linear or quadratic model (Fig. 4) based on the standard deviation (Table 5). As log *K^M* for amino-protons passes through a minimum with 1/*D*, an empirical quadratic model is attempted.

Since it has been found that *n_x* (mole fraction of DMSO) is a non-linear function of 1/*D* (Fig. 3), a similar empirical polynomial is tried for the variation of log β_{011} , log (β_{012}/β_{011}) and log (β_{013}/β_{012}) for L-dopa and log β_{011} , log (β_{012}/β_{011}) for L-alanine with *n_x* of aquo-DMSO (Fig. 5). These empirical models can be used to predict the equilibrium constants of these complexes at desired cosolvent composition or in isodielectric media, provided electrostatic interactions alone play a major role in transfer of free energy. The number of water molecules released in stepwise protonation equilibria (Table 5) are calculated as described earlier²⁶, except that the values of *j* (an empirical parameter) are varied from -5 to +5 with unit increments. The best of several linear equations is arrived based on maximum

Fig. 3. Variation of $1/D$ with $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ and n_x : (O) $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ and (Δ) n_x .

TABLE 5—STANDARD DEVIATIONS FOR EMPIRICAL MODE OF VARIATION OF $\log K$ AND $1/D$ AND n_x *

	$1/D$		n_x		Number of water molecules released
	Linear	Quadratic	Linear	Quadratic	
L-Alanine					
COOH	0.189 0	0.061 9 ^a	0.067 3	0.056 03 ^a	3.0
NH ₃ ⁺	—	0.069 4 ^a	—	0.053 2 ^a	3.0
L-Dopa					
COOH	0.057 1 ^a	0.058 3	0.071 8	0.052 3 ^a	3.0
φ-OH	0.040 1	0.030 1 ^a	0.030 8 ^a	0.033 9	2.0
NH ₃ ⁺	—	0.167 0 ^a	—	0.121 8 ^a	3.0

*Best fit.

corrected correlation coefficient (CCC) and minimum standard deviation (SD) and a typical set of results are given in Table 6.

It is observed that there is an increase in solubility of L-dopa in aquo-DMSO mixtures as compared to that in pure water. This reflects that in $\nu_{\text{LH}_3^+}^M$ (activity coefficient) and $\Delta G_f(\text{LH}_3^+)$ (change in the free energy transfer) are negative and the protonated base, LH_3^+ ,

Fig. 4. Empirical model of variation of $\log \beta$ with $1/D$: (A) and (C) (---) linear, and (B) and (D) (—) quadratic; experimental point with 3 SD limits.

has a lower free energy in solvent mixture than in water, indicating specific solute-solvent interactions. Since protonated amine loses its proton only after a pH 9 in the case of L-alanine and L-dopa cationic end ($-\text{NH}_3^+$) undergoes solvation with DMSO. This is due to the fact that positive end of DMSO dipole which corresponds to the position of sulphur atom is shielded^{2,4} by the two methyl groups, rendering it more facile for nucleophilic solvation. The alternative model of the medium in vogue for explaining these short range or chemical interactions assumes the solvent to be an anisotropic inhomogeneous one. Further, this model explains strong dipole-dipole interactions and concentration fluctuations in multi-component solute-solvent systems. In spite of the fact, cooperative (communal) solute-solvent interactions^{2,5} which predominate beyond the first solvation shell contribute to the change in total free

Fig. 5. Empirical model of variation of $\log \beta$ with n_x : (A) and (C) (---) linear, and (B) and (D) (—) quadratic; experimental point with 3 SD limits.

energy transfer, it is rather difficult to split the non-electrostatic contributions into its constituent parts.

Thus, the solvation process can be understood as the formation of cavity of appropriate size in aquo-

TABLE 6—LINEAR TREND ANALYSIS OF $\log ([H_2O]/[S])$ vs $j^* \log [S] + \log \beta_1$, FOR ACIDO-BASIC EQUILIBRIA OF AMINO PROTON OF L-DOPA

J	Slope	S.D.	C.C.C.	SI	FEHR
-5	2.302 3	0.347 7	0.908 8	0.104 2	0.279 6
-4	1.639 7	0.304 0	0.847 8	0.151 1	0.336 6
-3	0.977 0	0.260 6	0.756 1	0.278 7	0.457 2
-2	0.314 4	0.217 4	0.253 5	0.853 2	0.797 9
-1	-0.348 2	0.174 9	0.435 5	0.645 3	0.695 6
0	-1.011 1	0.133 6	0.928 7	0.081 3	0.248 9
1	-1.673 5	0.095 1	0.986 2	0.015 8	0.108 9
2	-2.396 5	0.647 0	0.998 2	0.003 8	0.052 4
3	-2.998 8	0.057 2	0.998 4	0.001 8	0.036 8
4	-3.681 4	0.079 3	0.978 0	0.002 3	0.041 7
2	-4.324 0	0.115 0	0.996 9	0.003 5	0.051 3

* $0.00 < SI < 0.002$ and $FEHR < 0.10$ indicate best fit of the model; C.C.C. (corrected correlation coefficient) = $1 - (NP - 1) (RSS/TSS/(NP - 2))$; SI = Exner parameter = $(RSS/[(NP - 2) * TSS])^{1/2}$; FEHR = Ehreusen parameter =

$$\xi (RSS/TSS)^{1/2}; RSS = \text{residual sum of squares} = \sum_{i=1}^{NP} (Y_{obs}(i) - Y_{res}(i))^2; TSS = \text{total sum of squares} = \sum_{i=1}^{NP} (Y_{obs}(i) - Y_{mean})^2.$$

DMSO medium followed by the introduction of amino acid into the cavity²⁶.

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